

Content of Radiocaesium in Imported Fruits Sold on the Bulgarian Market

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Abstract

Monitoring of radiocaesium content in imported cultivated and forest fruits for the production of foods intended for the Bulgarian market and for export was carried out in the period 2021-2022.

The specific activity of the radionuclide determined in all samples was below the maximum permissible value of 600 Bq/kg, specified in EU regulation 2020/1158, being in the cultivated fruits below the minimum detectable activity (MDA).

In forest fruits, the highest content of radiocaesium was measured in bilberries, followed by cranberries and the wild blackberries.

Relatively higher values of the specific activity of Cs-137 were measured in bilberry samples imported from Ukraine, Belarus and Poland.

Keywords: radiocaesium, radioactivity of berries

Introduction

Accumulation of radionuclides in food and raw materials intended for subsequent processing can increase radioactive dose load in humans. Different radioactive elements accumulate in different organs of human body and, depending on their radiotoxicity, may cause pathological changes of varying degrees.

As a result of the Chernobyl accident in 1986, a significant amount of radioactive waste was released in the environment. Radioactive pollution was spread across the territory of the whole European continent in different degree depending on meteorological conditions and the movement of polluted air masses. Deposition of radioactive caesium was 29 PBq in Russia, 15 PBq in Belarus, 13 PBq in Ukraine, and another 27 PBq in other European countries (De Cort et al., 1998).

Physical and chemical properties of radiocaesium are similar to those of potassium. Due to its good solubility in water, caesium is very well absorbed and distributed relatively evenly in the body (Beňová et al., 2016).

The use of various fruits, especially such as the bilberry, in which accumulation of radioactive elements is found (Yablokov, 2009, Kienzl et al., 1992), both for direct consumption and for the production of various food products, requires regular radioecological monitoring.

The EU Regulation 2020/1158 on the conditions governing imports of food and feed originating in third countries following the accident at the Chernobyl nuclear power station (Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2020/1158, 2020) specifies the following maximum permissible values for the content of caesium-137 in food:

- 370 Bq/kg for milk and milk products and for foods for infants and small children;
- 600 Bq/kg for all other products.

Monitoring of radiocaesium content in imported cultivated and wild forest fruits was carried out in the period 2021–2022 to ensure the safety of food products intended for the national market and export.

Materials and Methods

The plant samples tested in the Laboratory in the period 2021 – 2022 included:

- cultivated fruits (frozen and fresh) – strawberries, sour cherries and raspberries;
- forest fruits (frozen and fresh) – bilberries, cranberries, blackberries, wild raspberries, wild strawberries, black elderberries and blackcurrant.

The samples were imported from Sweden, Poland, Latvia, Romania, Serbia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Turkey, Belarus and Ukraine. The total number of tested samples was 89.

Specific activity of Cs-134 and Cs-137 was determined gamma-spectrometrically by the full energy peaks of both radionuclides, $E_{\gamma} = 604.7$ kV (quantum yield – 97.6%) and $E_{\gamma} = 661.6$ kV (quantum yield – 85.1%), respectively. The measurement system is product of CANBERRA and includes a DSA1000 multichannel analyzer, pure germanium detector (30% relative efficiency and 1.3 KeV resolution of Co-60 full energy peak at 1332 kV), and GENNIE2K software. The samples were measured in Marinelli-type container of 450 cm³ volume.

Results and Discussion

Results of the study carried out in 2021 and 2022 are summarized in Table 1.

The specific activity of the radioactive isotope cesium-134 in all samples was below the minimum detectable activity (MDA), which was expected due to the relatively short half-life of the radionuclide – 2.06 years. This is an evidence that no other deposition of radioactive caesium occurred as a result of fallout or nuclear accidents after the contamination from the Chernobyl accident.

In all fruits analyzed, the specific activity of cesium-137 was lower than the maximum permissible value of 600 Bq/kg specified in Regulation 2020/1158 of EU. The content of the radioisotope was below the minimum detectable activity (MDA) in all cultivated plants.

Cultivated lands are subjected to various tillage as rotational plowing, discing, harrowing, etc. This leads to a significant decrease in the activity concentration of Cs-137 in the upper 10 cm layer of the soil, where the main exchange processes between the plant root system and soil take place (Paramonova et al., 2017). The availability of cesium-137 to plants in arable soils is mainly influenced by the content of clay minerals and the amount of exchangeable potassium. The weathered edges of illitic and micaceous tactoids fraction are the main adsorbent of radiocaesium in the soil and potassium is the main competitor for the specific positions in the soil absorption complex (Absalom et al., 1999). In soils with high clay content, cesium is rapidly immobilized and its bioavailability to plants decrease.

In berries grown on forest soils, however, an increase in the content of cesium-137 was found, being highest in the bilberry, followed by the wild blackberry and the cranberry.

Compared to agricultural lands, forests are complex ecosystems that include several vegetation layers (trees, shrubs, grasses and other annual plants) and multilayered soil profiles (forest litter, semi-organic and mineral layers) leading to different redistribution of radionuclides (Calmon et al., 2009). In undisturbed soils, radiocesium is mainly concentrated in the upper 0-5 and 5-10 cm layers of the soil (Yordanova et al., 2016; Yordanova et al., 2014), making the radionuclide potentially accessible to the root system of plants. An additional factor is the higher contamination of areas of higher altitudes.

Table 1. Content of ^{137}Cs in imported fruits

№	Plant type	Origin	Number of samples	^{137}Cs Bq.kg ⁻¹	
				Min	Max
1	Cultivated raspberry	Serbia	3	< 1	< 1
2	Wild raspberry	Serbia	3	< 1	< 1
3	Sour cherry	Serbia	7	< 1	< 1
4	Cultivated strawberry	Turkey	6	< 1	< 1
5	Cultivated strawberry	Ukraine	2	< 1	< 1
6	Wild strawberry	Montenegro	1	< 1	< 1
7	Wild strawberry	Serbia	1	< 1	< 1
		Bosna and Herzegovina			
8	Wild black strawberry		1	< 1	< 1
9	Blackcurrant	Latvia	2	< 1	< 1
10	Black elderberry	Romania	1	< 1	< 1
		Bosna and Herzegovina			
11	Black elderberry		1	< 1	< 1
12	Wild blackberry	Romania	5	< 1	11±2
13	Wild blackberry	Ukraine	2	< 1	30±4
14	Wild bilberry	Sweden	4	< 1	< 1
13	Wild bilberry	Romania	23	< 1	15±3
15	Wild bilberry	Poland	5	6±1	180±20
16	Wild bilberry	Ukraine	10	5±1	250±30
17	Wild bilberry	Belarus	2	40±8	210±10
17	Wild cranberry	Romania	7	< 1	25±4
18	Wild cranberry	Poland	1	6±2	6±2
19	Wild cranberry	Ukraine	2	3±1	5±1

Another factor that can lead to the accumulation of radiocesium in the bilberry in particular (*Vaccinum specie.*) is the fact that it belongs to the Ericaceae family, which is characterized by a specific root system growing horizontally within the first few centimeters of the organic layer of the soil, formed by endotrophic mycorrhiza, contributing to the mobilization and absorption of mineral salts from the soil (Calabrese et al. 2018, Ehlken et al., 2002). Higher levels of cesium-137 were found in the cranberry belonging to Ericaceae family too.

Furthermore the higher acidity of forest soils may contribute to the re-mobilization of radiocesium from the soil and increase its availability to the plant.

Average value and median were calculated with the data obtained for the ^{137}Cs specific activity higher than MDA found in bilberries imported from Romania, Poland and Ukraine. Results are presented in figure 1.

Figure 1. Average value and median of the specific activity of radiocesium in bilberries imported from different countries in Bq.kg^{-1}

The highest content of radiocaesium was found in bilberries from Ukraine, followed Belarus, Poland and Romania, as the median data for Ukraine tended to the higher values of the measured specific activities, while in Poland - to the lower.

The accident at the Chernobyl Nuclear Power Plant resulted in the radioactive contamination of 3.5 million hectares of Ukrainian forests. Soil contamination of the forest massifs with caesium radioisotopes ranged from 37 to 5,200 kBq/m^2 . The most polluted was the region of Polisia, where the area of forests with pollution over 37 kBq/m^2 amounted to 1141.6 thousand hectares (Landin, 2013). In the years after the accident, as a result of the physical decay of radioisotopes, as well under the influence of migration processes, the radiation situation in forest ecosystems significantly changed, as the change depended on a number of factors - homogeneity of the deposition, physical and agrochemical properties of the soils and isotopic composition of the radioactive waste.

The data on the specific activity of radiocaesium in bilberries, collected mainly in the northern regions of Ukraine (Chernihiv, Kyiv, Zhytomyr, Volyn, Khmelnytskyi, Vinnytsia and Zakarpattia regions), cited by Buzynnyi et al. ranged between 69 and 766 Bq/kg (Buzynnyi et al., 2019). Other authors reported even higher values of $1091+331.90 \text{ Bq/kg}$ in bilberries from Zhytomyr Region, Ukraine, situated 70 km from the Chernobyl NPP (Davydova et al., 2020). In six batches of bilberries imported from Ukraine intended for the production of jams in Italy, values between $43 \pm 15\%$ and $350 \pm 5\% \text{ Bq/kg}$ were measured (Calabrese et al., 2018).

For Poland, Grabowski et al. reported values of 100 Bq/kg in 1986 and 50 Bq/kg in 1999 for radiocesium content in bilberries collected from different regions of the country, observed regularly on an annual basis (Grabowski et al., 2000).

Belarus was one of the countries which was also heavily affected by the radioactive contamination following the Chernobyl accident. Pollution of forest lands amounted to 23%, decreasing to 16% by 2021. Chernushevich et al. reported data on radiocesium content between 36

and 510 Bq/kg measured in 32 samples of bilberries collected from different regions of Belarus (Chernushevich et al., 2021). In the samples of bilberries imported from Belarus and analyzed in the present study, the content of cesium-137 was between 40 ± 8 and 210 ± 10 Bq/kg.

The results in the present study are comparable to the data from the above-mentioned countries cited by other authors.

Missik et al. cited specific activity of 535.7 ± 29.8 Bq.kg⁻¹ in bilberries imported from Romania (Missik et al., 2006). These values were higher than the obtained in the present study (from <1 to 15 ± 3). The difference was probably both due to the physical decay of radiocesium and the heterogeneity of its deposition.

Conclusion

The results of the study carried out showed the content of technogenic caesium-137 was below the maximum permissible value of 600 Bq/kg specified in Regulation 2020/1158 of EU in all tested fruits and it can be concluded that they are safe for human consumption both fresh and processed to various food products.

In the cultivated fruits, the measured specific activity of the radioisotope was below the minimum detectable activity.

At the same time, from the data obtained in 2021 and 2022, it can be seen that despite the 37 years period after the Chernobyl accident, well detectable amounts of Cs-137 can still be found in forest fruits such as blackberry, cranberry and bilberry. This requires their radiological monitoring to be carried out on a regular basis, especially on fruits imported from Ukraine, Belarus and Poland.

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